

Droop-Control-Aided State Estimation in Active Distribution Systems

Stelios C. Dimoulias
School of Electr. & Comput. Eng.
Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
Thessaloniki, Greece
steliosd@ece.auth.gr

Georgios C. Kryonidis
School of Electr. & Comput. Eng.
Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
Thessaloniki, Greece
kryonidi@ece.auth.gr

Kyriaki-Nefeli D. Malamaki
School of Electr. & Comput. Eng.
Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
Thessaloniki, Greece
kyriaki_nefeli@hotmail.com

Eleftherios O. Kontis
School of Electr. & Comput. Eng.
University of Thessaly
Volos, Greece
elkontis@uth.gr

Fotios P. Fotellis
Grid Oper. & Develop.
Hellenic Distrib. Netw. Oper.
Thessaloniki, Greece
fotfotellis@gmail.com

Apostolos N. Milioudis
Grid Oper. & Develop.
Hellenic Distrib. Netw. Oper.
Thessaloniki, Greece
a.milioudis@deddie.gr

Esther Romero-Ramos
Dept. of Electr. Eng.
Universidad de Sevilla
Seville, Spain
eromero@us.es

Abstract—In this paper, an enhanced state estimation algorithm for active distribution systems (DSs) is presented. Its distinct characteristic is the integration of the local control logic of the distributed renewable energy sources, i.e., the droop control, into the mathematical formulation of the state estimation problem. Numerical results on a real medium-voltage DS are presented to highlight the superior performance of the proposed method against the conventional weighted least squares estimation algorithm in terms of increased accuracy and observability.

Index Terms—Distributed renewable energy sources, distribution system state estimation, droop control, photovoltaic units, weighted least squares.

I. INTRODUCTION

Monitoring and control can be regarded as the main cornerstones of the smart grid paradigm, facilitating the proliferation of distributed renewable energy sources (DRESs) toward a green and sustainable electricity grid [1]. Focusing on the former, the robustness of the monitoring schemes can be enhanced by employing state estimation techniques, which serve to remove measurement noise, bad data, as well as deliberately injected false data in case of cybersecurity breaches [2].

In the literature, several distribution system state estimation (DSSE) solutions have been proposed, which can be classified into two main categories: machine learning methods and robust optimization methods. The first category involves the use of machine learning techniques trained on a set of historically available measurements, without prior knowledge of the distribution system (DS) configuration. Specifically, an unrolled

spatiotemporal graph convolutional network is proposed in [3] to incorporate the spatiotemporal correlations of the measurements into the state estimation (SE) process. A similar approach is presented in [4], which, however, introduces the DS topology as a trainable parameter. To avoid the excessive computational burden in the training process posed by the lack of knowledge related to the DS configuration, as well as to further increase the accuracy of data-driven DSSE methods, physics-informed solutions have recently been proposed [5], [6]. In [5], an enhanced neural network is introduced by integrating the DS admittance matrix in the training process. This idea has been further developed in [6], by considering the DS topology changes in the analysis.

In the second category, robust optimization techniques are applied to solve the DSSE problem, focusing on improving the calculation performance and the solution accuracy. In particular, the authors in [7] use the powerful Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm to solve the DSSE problem. Moreover, the well-established backward-forward sweep method is used in [8] to prevent ill-conditioning issues and ensure robust convergence along with low computational burden. In [9], the conventional weighted least squares (WLS) method is replaced by two robust regression estimators to improve the solution accuracy. A two time-scale approach is presented in [10] to handle different types of measurements used in the DSSE. Furthermore, to overcome the increased computational complexity caused by the inherent nonlinearities, linearization techniques based on the Taylor series and the linear programming contractor are used in [11] and [12], respectively. Finally, in [13], an enhanced initialization process is proposed, using a

This research is funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe project COCOON (GA 101120221).

neural network to accelerate the convergence and improve the stability and accuracy of the robust optimization algorithm.

As a common drawback, all the above methods neglect the local control logic of DRESs, e.g., droop control, which could provide additional insights into the DSSE. Only a few works have addressed this aspect, i.e., [14] and [15], albeit solely focusing on the islanded operation of microgrids. Additionally, although the authors in [16] state that droop control schemes are included in the DSSE, the therein analysis lacks a thorough investigation in terms of both numerical results and discussion.

Based on the above, the scope of this paper is to address this gap by proposing an enhanced DSSE method for DSs with high DRES penetration. The main characteristic is the inclusion of the local control logic, i.e., droop control, of the DRESs in the mathematical formulation of the DSSE problem. By conducting simulations on a real medium-voltage (MV) DS located in Greece, the performance of the proposed method is evaluated against the conventional WLS solution in terms of both accuracy and observability.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section II presents the mathematical background of the proposed DSSE method. Subsequently, the system under study is briefly discussed in Section III, followed by the presentation of the numerical results in Section IV. Finally, Section V concludes the paper by highlighting the main findings and discussing directions for future research.

II. PROPOSED METHOD

In a power system with $N+1$ buses and M available measurements, the formulation of any state estimation (SE) problem can be encapsulated by (1).

$$\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}) + \mathbf{e} \quad (1)$$

Here, \mathbf{x} is the $2N \times 1$ vector of system states, \mathbf{z} denotes the $M \times 1$ vector of measured quantities, $\mathbf{h}(\cdot)$ represents the non-linear set of functions correlating \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{z} , and \mathbf{e} is the $M \times 1$ vector of measurement errors. If the set of functions $\mathbf{h}(\cdot)$ is approximated by a $M \times 2N$ Jacobian matrix, \mathbf{H} , the linear (DC) SE problem formulation is derived, as presented in (2).

$$\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{e} \quad (2)$$

The proposed DSSE formulation considers a radial, active DS of $N+1$ buses, comprising the set \mathcal{N} , with subsets \mathcal{M}_P , \mathcal{M}_Q , and \mathcal{M}_V representing the buses with active power, reactive power, and voltage magnitude measurements, respectively. Moreover, subset \mathcal{N}_{DRES} contains the buses with DRES units and subset \mathcal{N}_{zero} represents the zero-injection buses of the system. P_i , Q_i , and V_i denote the estimated values of active and reactive power injection and voltage magnitude at bus $i \in \mathcal{N}$, respectively, while \hat{P}_i , \hat{Q}_i , and \hat{V}_i denote the corresponding measured values, if available. The measurements are assumed to be affected by additive errors of zero mean value and standard deviation σ_{P_i} , σ_{Q_i} , and σ_{V_i} , respectively. Based on the above and assuming that the DRES units operate under

a $Q(V)$ droop control scheme, the proposed DSSE method is mathematically formulated as follows:

$$\min \sum_{i \in \mathcal{M}_P} \frac{(P_i - \hat{P}_i)^2}{\sigma_{P_i}^2} + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{M}_Q} \frac{(Q_i - \hat{Q}_i)^2}{\sigma_{Q_i}^2} + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{M}_V} \frac{(V_i - \hat{V}_i)^2}{\sigma_{V_i}^2} \quad (3)$$

s.t.

$$V_i = f(\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{Q}, V_{\text{prev},i}), i \in \mathcal{N} \quad (4)$$

$$P_i = Q_i = 0, i \in \mathcal{N}_{zero} \quad (5)$$

$$P_0 = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}, i \neq 0} P_i + P_{\text{loss,tot}}, \quad Q_0 = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}, i \neq 0} Q_i + Q_{\text{loss,tot}} \quad (6)$$

$$Q_i = g(V_i), i \in \mathcal{N}_{DRES} \quad (7)$$

Eq. (3) is the WLS objective function, (4) represents the non-linear power flow relationships, as formulated in [17], and (5) exploits the a-priori knowledge regarding the zero-injection buses of the DS. Eq. (6) expresses the power balance, where P_0 , Q_0 are the active and reactive power provided by the slack bus, and $P_{\text{loss,tot}}$, $Q_{\text{loss,tot}}$ denote the sums of active and reactive power losses within the DS. In (4), vectors \mathbf{P} , \mathbf{Q} aggregate the P_i , Q_i quantities, respectively, while $V_{\text{prev},i}$ denotes the voltage of the bus directly upstream of bus i .

The advancement with regard to the conventional WLS state estimators is introduced by the consideration of the local control logic of the DRES units. This is reflected in the inclusion of (7), which expresses the piece-wise linear $Q(V)$ droop characteristic of the DRES plants, as recommended in [18] and illustrated in Fig. 1. In Fig. 1, positive/negative reactive power values indicate injection/absorption, respectively, while per unit (pu) values refer to the rated power of each DRES.

Furthermore, it should be noted that (7), along with the general DSSE formulation, could be appropriately modified, if DRES units were to operate under $P(V)$ or $\cos\varphi(V)$ control schemes. In this study, the $Q(V)$ droop was considered, without loss of generality.

III. SYSTEM UNDER STUDY

The examined system is a radial MV DS in Greece. The DS comprises 48 buses, among which 16 host a DRES unit (\mathcal{N}_{DRES}) and 32 are zero-injection buses (\mathcal{N}_{zero}), as illustrated in Fig. 2. The nominal voltage of the DS is 20 kV, while the DRESs are connected at the level of 0.4 kV. The voltage of the upstream system is 150 kV. The characteristics of the lines and the transformers are reported in Tables I and II, respectively. The rated power, $S_{r,i}$, of the DRESs is presented in Table III. Regarding the operating points of the DRESs, reactive power is determined by the droop curve of Fig. 1, as per [18]. As depicted in Fig. 1, the maximum foreseen reactive power of a DRES unit, $Q_{max,i}$ is defined by (8). Thus, the active power operating point of each DRES, P_i^{true} , is set according to (9), to allow for the provision of $Q_{max,i}$.

$$Q_{max,i} = 0.44 \cdot S_{r,i}, i \in \mathcal{N}_{DRES} \quad (8)$$

$$P_i^{true} = \sqrt{S_{r,i}^2 - Q_{max,i}^2}, i \in \mathcal{N}_{DRES} \quad (9)$$

Fig. 1. Considered $Q(V)$ characteristic.

Fig. 2. System under study

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this section, the proposed DSSE method is compared against the conventional one, with respect to accuracy and observability.

A. Impact on Accuracy

The accuracy of the proposed and the conventional DSSE models is comparatively assessed under realistic noise conditions in DSs. Specifically, values of $\sigma_{P_i}=0.012$, $\sigma_{Q_i}=0.015$, and $\sigma_{V_i}=0.01$, in pu, are assumed. These standard deviations are derived according to the maximum permissible percentage error values for active power, reactive power, and voltage magnitude measurements, as described in [19], [20], and [21], respectively, and considering a confidence interval of 95%.

For the considered values of σ_{P_i} , σ_{Q_i} , and σ_{V_i} , 100 Monte Carlo (MC) scenarios are examined, emulating discrete instances of measurement errors. In all scenarios, \hat{P}_i , \hat{Q}_i , and \hat{V}_i measurements at the DRES buses are assumed. For each estimated quantity, X_i , the accuracy of the DSSE is evaluated by the absolute percentage error, APE_{X_i} , defined as follows:

$$APE_{X_i}(\%) = \frac{|X_i - X_i^{true}|}{X_i^{true}} \cdot 100\%, i \in \mathcal{N} \quad (10)$$

Elaborating, in (10), X_i could represent either P_i , Q_i , or V_i , depending on the estimated quantity, while X_i^{true} denotes the true value of this quantity.

The $APE_{X_i}(\%)$ values concerning the DRES buses, for an indicative MC case, are presented in Table IV. As shown, for reactive power estimates, the proposed method reduces the $APE_{Q_i}(\%)$ for as much as two orders of magnitude compared to the conventional approach, while a reduction of one order of

TABLE I
LINE CHARACTERISTICS

Lines	R (Ω)	X (Ω)
1-2	2.81	3.11
2-3, 6-7, 6-9, 9-10, 9-12, 12-15, 17-18, 21-24, 21-22, 26-27, 29-30, 32-33, 35-36, 38-39, 41-42, 44-47	0.576	0.4
2-5	0.83	1.06
5-6	0.33	0.23
12-13	0.12	0.08
5-17, 26-29, 29-32, 32-35, 35-38, 38-41, 41-44, 44-45	0.21	0.33
17-20	0.167	1.06
20-21	0.323	0.22
20-26	0.85	1.32

TABLE II
TRANSFORMER CHARACTERISTICS

Transformer	r_k (%)	x_k (%)	S_r (MVA)
0-1	15.7	0.14	20
3-4, 10-11, 15-16, 18-19, 24-25, 22-23, 33-34, 36-37	5.92	1	1
47-48, 45-46	5.92	1	0.8
27-28, 39-40, 42-43	5.87	1.2	0.5
7-8, 13-14, 30-31	5.87	1.2	0.4

TABLE III
DRES RATED POWER

$i \in \mathcal{N}_{DRES}$	$S_{r,i}$ (MVA)
8	0.37
14, 31	0.41
28, 40, 43	0.52
46	0.76
48	0.83
4	0.9
34	0.97
11, 16, 19, 23, 25, 37	1.04

magnitude is achieved for the $APE_{V_i}(\%)$, per bus. Regarding the $APE_{P_i}(\%)$, a slight improvement in the DSSE accuracy is observed, albeit not substantial.

The overall improvement of the DSSE accuracy, as evaluated by means of the 100 MC simulations, is illustrated in Fig. 3. More specifically, Fig. 3 depicts the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the $APE_{X_i}(\%)$, as computed for all buses and MC cases, for the estimates of active power, reactive power, and voltage magnitude. As demonstrated in Fig. 3b and Fig. 3c, the proposed method leads to considerably lower APE_{X_i} values for the reactive power and voltage estimates. This improved accuracy is mathematically explained by the introduction of (7). More specifically, additional information on the correlation between voltage and reactive power is ex-

TABLE IV
COMPARISON OF APE_{X_i} (%), $i \in \mathcal{N}_{DRES}$

i	Conventional method			Proposed method		
	P_i	Q_i	V_i	P_i	Q_i	V_i
4	0.42	8.69	0.015	0.4	1.04	0.0028
8	3.53	23.05	0.187	3.43	0.78	0.0243
11	0.46	3.06	0.021	0.45	0.28	0.0032
14	1.82	10.3	0.092	1.78	0.74	0.0036
16	0.52	4.24	0.042	0.5	0.08	0.0077
19	1.44	8.65	0.078	1.4	0.32	0.0013
23	0.75	5.76	0.057	0.73	0.01	0.0092
25	0.3	1.91	0.009	0.3	0.2	0.0046
28	0.25	1.28	0.004	0.24	0.21	0.0038
31	1.57	7.61	0.096	1.53	0.24	0.0154
37	1.13	8.99	0.062	1.1	0.45	0.0011
40	3.73	18.91	0.228	3.61	0.75	0.0268
43	4.9	24.83	0.297	4.76	0.99	0.0333
46	1.05	5.91	0.047	1.02	0.26	0.0027
48	0.67	3.79	0.029	0.65	0.19	0.0042

ploited, reinforcing the estimation of the same state variables.

Concerning the active power estimates, the estimation accuracy is slightly increased, as attested by Fig. 3a. The minor amelioration of the active power estimation is not surprising, as there is no additional set of equations directly involving the active power in the proposed method.

In conclusion, the additional information regarding the droop control scheme, as leveraged by the proposed method, allows for a more accurate estimation of all quantities of interest in a DS, with a particular upgrade in reactive power and voltage estimation. Special emphasis should be given to the enhancement of the reactive power estimation, as the conventional method yields quite important APE_{Q_i} values, as indicated by both Table IV and Fig. 3b. This poor performance of the conventional method is attributed to the structure of the WLS estimator and the deficient accuracy of the reactive power meters, as expressed by the high σ_{Q_i} value. Nonetheless, the proposed method addresses this inherent drawback of the WLS estimator and considerably improves the reactive power estimation. This is of significant importance in modern DS, as the DS operators (DSOs) need to reliably monitor the exchange of reactive power by the DRESs, to ensure that each DRES operates according to the expected droop curve and the voltage regulation is performed as planned. After all, the operation of DRESs under a $Q(V)$ droop is an ancillary service, whose fair remuneration requires reliable monitoring.

B. Impact on Observability

The impact of the proposed method on the observability of the examined DS is quantified by the minimum required number of measurements. More specifically, the observability of a system is expressed by the column rank of matrix \mathbf{H} ; if \mathbf{H} is of full-column rank, the system is observable. Therefore, for any system of $N+1$ buses, the minimum required number

Fig. 3. CDFs of the APE for a) active power, b) reactive power, and c) voltage magnitude, for the proposed and the conventional method.

of measurements is $M_{min} = 2N$, as any other number of measurements would evidently render \mathbf{H} rank-deficient.

Theoretically, an unobservable system requires additional measurements to become observable. From a mathematical perspective, the incorporation of additional measurements translates into an increase in the number of rows in vector \mathbf{z} and matrix \mathbf{H} . Alternatively, the implementation of the proposed method achieves the same effect, thanks to the inclusion of (7) and without the need for additional measurements. More specifically, under the proposed method, the measurement Jacobian matrix becomes $\mathbf{H}_{aug} = [\mathbf{H}^T \mathbf{H}_{droop}^T]^T$, with \mathbf{H} denoting the measurement Jacobian matrix corresponding to the conventional method and \mathbf{H}_{droop} the matrix that represents the additional droop control equations.

For the examined DS, $N = 48$, and hence, $M_{min} = 96$. Indeed, the availability of \hat{P}_i, \hat{Q}_i for any set of 48 buses, out of the 49 in total, ensures observability. In practical terms, by leveraging the reliable information regarding the zero-injection buses and reasonably assuming the availability of the P_0, Q_0 measurements at the substation, the system becomes observable if power meters are installed at least at any 15 out of the 16 DRES buses, measuring active and reactive power. Therefore, the conventional method needs 30 measurements, which along with the substation measurements and the virtual measurements for the zero-injection buses, constitute the 96 required measurements.

Conversely, the proposed method augments \mathbf{z} and \mathbf{H} , as each available voltage measurement at a DRES bus introduces an additional equation. Consequently, under the implemen-

TABLE V
MINIMUM OBSERVABILITY REQUIREMENTS

Method	Measurements Number	Meter Type
Conventional	30	Power meters
Proposed	15	Voltage sensors

tation of the proposed method, the installation of voltage sensors at any 15 out of the 16 DRES buses suffices for the observability of the system. Elaborating, in this case, the number of measurements is 15. Thus, the consideration of the substation and virtual measurements would elevate the total number of measurements, and the rank of \mathbf{H} , to 81, which is deficient. Nevertheless, the rank of the actual Jacobian matrix, \mathbf{H}_{aug} , is 96, thanks to the inclusion of (7), hence mathematically validating the possession of sufficient information to perform the DSSE. The minimum observability requirements under the conventional and the proposed method are summarized in Table V.

Therefore, the proposed method can ensure the observability of the system with a simpler type of metering device, i.e., voltage sensors instead of active/reactive power meters, and fewer measurements, i.e., 15 instead of 30. This translates into significantly lower expenditure and data load. Specifically, voltage sensors are considerably cheaper than active/reactive power meters, as the latter also imply the existence of current sensors. Moreover, reducing by half the required number of measurements results in lighter data traffic and relaxed data storage demands. Thus, the method addresses one of the main issues that decelerate the practical application of SE in DSs, namely the excessive data handling and data storage requirements, imposed by the size and complexity of DSs.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, an enhanced version of the conventional WLS state estimation method is introduced. The proposed method exploits the new operational paradigm of DRES, which often operate under a $Q(V)$ droop control scheme, to achieve improved accuracy and observability. The performance of the method is tested on a real, active MV DS located in Greece. Firstly, the accuracy of the method is comparatively evaluated against that of the conventional SE formulation, by means of MC simulations under realistic noise conditions. The conducted statistical analysis reveals the superior performance of the proposed method, which achieves higher estimation accuracy for all monitored quantities and especially for reactive power and voltage. Subsequently, the capability of the method to ensure the observability of the monitored DS under limited financial and data resources is validated. Thanks to its relative advantages, the proposed method could facilitate the application of DSSE, allowing for the reliable monitoring of modern, active DSs. Future research will focus on testing the method over DSs of increased complexity, different measurement noise characteristics, and asynchronous

measurements. Additionally, more sophisticated and robust estimators, apart from WLS one, will be investigated.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Primadianto and C.-N. Lu, "A review on distribution system state estimation," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 32, no. 5, pp. 3875–3883, 2017.
- [2] K. Dehghanpour, Z. Wang, J. Wang, Y. Yuan, and F. Bu, "A survey on state estimation techniques and challenges in smart distribution systems," *IEEE Trans. Smart Grid*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 2312–2322, 2019.
- [3] H. Wu, Z. Xu, and M. Wang, "Unrolled spatiotemporal graph convolutional network for distribution system state estimation and forecasting," *IEEE Trans. Sustain. Energy*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 297–308, 2023.
- [4] D. Cao, J. Zhao, W. Hu, Q. Liao, Q. Huang, and Z. Chen, "Topology change aware data-driven probabilistic distribution state estimation based on gaussian process," *IEEE Trans. Smart Grid*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 1317–1320, 2023.
- [5] A. S. Zamzam and N. D. Sidiropoulos, "Physics-aware neural networks for distribution system state estimation," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 35, no. 6, pp. 4347–4356, 2020.
- [6] D. Cao, J. Zhao, W. Hu, N. Yu, J. Hu, and Z. Chen, "Physics-informed graphical learning and bayesian averaging for robust distribution state estimation," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 39, no. 2, pp. 2879–2892, 2024.
- [7] E. B. Alzate, M. Bueno-López, J. Xie, and K. Strunz, "Distribution system state estimation to support coordinated voltage-control strategies by using smart meters," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 34, no. 6, pp. 5198–5207, 2019.
- [8] M. Pau and Z. Tamim, "A backward-forward sweep algorithm for distribution system state estimation," *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.*, vol. 72, pp. 1–11, 2023.
- [9] A. G. Miles, Y. Chakhchoukh, and S. M. S. Alam, "Robust distribution state estimation for reliable locational marginal pricing under cyber-attacks," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 39, no. 3, pp. 4963–4974, 2024.
- [10] A. Gómez-Expósito, C. Gómez-Quiles, and I. Džafić, "State estimation in two time scales for smart distribution systems," *IEEE Trans. Smart Grid*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 421–430, 2015.
- [11] Y. Zhang and J. Wang, "Towards highly efficient state estimation with nonlinear measurements in distribution systems," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 35, no. 3, pp. 2471–2474, 2020.
- [12] V. Ngo and W. Wu, "Linear programming contractor for interval distribution state estimation using RDM arithmetic," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 36, no. 3, pp. 2114–2126, 2021.
- [13] A. S. Zamzam, X. Fu, and N. D. Sidiropoulos, "Data-driven learning-based optimization for distribution system state estimation," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 34, no. 6, pp. 4796–4805, 2019.
- [14] F. Feng, P. Zhang, and Y. Zhou, "Authentic microgrid state estimation," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 37, no. 2, pp. 1657–1660, 2022.
- [15] K. Surendra, B. Das, and V. Pant, "Application of DG droop equations for state estimation of islanded AC microgrids," in *2024 Third Int. Conf. Power Control and Comput. Technol. (ICPC2T)*, 2024, pp. 669–673.
- [16] I. Tácsi, I. Vokony, B. Hartmann, and G. M. Péter, "Low voltage state estimation based operation analysis of smart distribution assets," in *2022 8th Int. Youth Conf. Energy (IYCE)*, 2022, pp. 1–6.
- [17] G. C. Kryonidis, C. S. Demoulias, and G. K. Papagiannis, "A nearly decentralized voltage regulation algorithm for loss minimization in radial mv networks with high dg penetration," *IEEE Trans. Sustain. Energy*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 1430–1439, 2016.
- [18] IEEE Std 1547-2018, "IEEE Standard for Interconnection and Interoperability of Distributed Energy Resources with Associated Electric Power Systems Interfaces," *IEEE Std 1547-2018 (Revision of IEEE Std 1547-2003)*, pp. 1–138, 2018.
- [19] IEC 62053-21, *Electricity metering equipment (a.c.) – Particular requirements – Part 21: Static meters for active energy (classes 1 and 2)*.
- [20] IEC 62053-23, *Electricity metering equipment (a.c.) – Particular requirements – Part 23: Static meters for reactive energy (classes 2 and 3)*.
- [21] IEC 61557-12, *Electrical safety in low voltage distribution systems up to 1 000 V a.c. and 1 500 V d.c. – Equipment for testing, measuring or monitoring of protective measures – Part 12: Performance measuring and monitoring devices (PMD)*.